

HORIZON 2020 - Coordination and Support Action

Grant Agreement No: 101003766

**EU-PolarNet 2 - Co-ordinating and Co-designing the
European Polar Research Area**

Deliverable No. D3.2

**Definition of the call for services incl. a selection
and evaluation scheme**

Submission of Deliverable

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PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY

EU-PolarNet 2 has developed a Call for services procedure, including eligibility and selection criteria and a review system, with the objective of seeking input from the Polar community to develop ideas for concrete European Polar research actions. This activity is part of the objective of WP3 to further develop existing European Polar research strategies and to advance European Polar research actions. The call has been prepared in close collaboration with the stakeholder guardian to ensure that the service contracts are also targeted to early engagement with stake- and rightholders. The deliverable output comprises different documents: guidelines for applicants with eligibility criteria, funding conditions and submission guidelines and the template submission form. Three calls for proposals will be launched in the coming three years.

1 Introduction

Within Work package 3 - Research Prioritisation, Task 3.3 will seek bottom-up input from the European Polar Community for the further development of European Polar research actions by launching three Calls for services.

The requested services will contribute to the research prioritisation process in Task 3.1 by Identifying key Polar research actions and to Task 3.2 for the development of large-scale Polar initiatives. Outputs of the Calls for services are desk studies or the organisation of workshops on specific themes to further specify topics defined in Tasks 3.1 and 3.2.

The Call for Services offers financial support of up to 15.000 € to cover expenses necessary for successfully implementing the proposed activities.

Applications are welcome from European researchers and/or stake- and rightholders. The inclusion of Early Career researchers and the formation of transdisciplinary networking between researchers and stake- and rightholders relevant to the topic and/or region is especially encouraged.

This first Call for Services has been launched on 1 July 2021 - <https://eu-polarnet.eu/call/>. The Call stays open for submissions until 30 September 2021.

The first call covers activities related to research needs 4 and 6 of the [European Polar Research Programme](#) (EPRP):

1. Better understanding of climate change in the Polar Regions and its links to lower latitudes
2. Informed weather and climate action
3. Resilient socio-ecological systems
- 4. Prospering communities in the Arctic**
5. Challenges and Opportunities for Polar Operations
- 6. Inclusive creation, access and usage of knowledge**

The other 4 research needs will be covered per two in the next two calls.

A webinar will be organised on 7 July 2021 to inform possible applicants how to apply for an EU-PolarNet 2 Service Contract.

2 Main Objectives

One of the objectives of EU-PolarNet 2 is to prioritise and specify the key societally relevant Polar research themes, which have been defined in the European Polar Research Programme (EPRP), the EU-PolarNet White Papers and in European Polar strategies.

With launching calls for services, EU-PolarNet 2 seeks support from the European Polar Community to further develop research ideas into achievable research projects that could be funded on a national, European or international level. The research themes in the different calls shall be based on the research needs defined in the [European Polar Research Programme](#) (EPRP) and shall contribute to specific key questions.

The first call covers activities related to research needs 4 and 6 of the [European Polar Research Programme](#) (EPRP):

- Prospering communities in the Arctic
- Inclusive creation, access and usage of knowledge

2.1 Prospering communities in the Arctic

This includes the following key questions:

- An infrastructure plan in support of sustainable community development.
- National and sub-national governance challenges in the Arctic Regions.
- Economic innovations for sustainable development of Arctic communities.
- Education as a tool to expand the capacity of Arctic residents to respond to changes.
- Learning from the past for a socio-economically balanced and gender-equal development of the Polar Regions.
- The demography of the future Arctic population.
- Cultural vitality for prosperity in the Arctic.

2.2 Inclusive creation, access and usage of knowledge

This includes the following key questions:

- Developing new technologies and improved capacities in observation, modelling, and research in the Polar regions.
- Co-production of knowledge as a benefit to societal stakeholders.
- FAIR data management principles for polar data collections.
- Ensuring knowledge access and capacity building in Polar Regions.
- Exploiting knowledge to inform decision making for the Polar Regions.

3 Implementation of the service contract

The implementation of the service contract will require tools and/or approaches to be effective and achieve its objectives. For example, site visits and conferences, workshops, desk studies, setting up networks, web interfaces or fora, platforms, measures to promote stakeholders' involvement, are all tools and approaches through which the project's objectives can be achieved.

4 Timing and budget

The duration of a service contract is 12 months maximum as of the signature of the contract, for a maximum budget of 15.000€. This budget is allocated to the service provider(s) and shall cover all expenses considered necessary for successfully implementing the proposed activities such as personnel, operational and travel costs.

The total budget of each call is 40.000€.

5 Selection procedure

The evaluation procedure and selection of research offers will be organised by the EU-PolarNet 2 consortium and performed by its Polar Expert Group (PEG). The PEG is the EU-PolarNet 2 Expert Forum for implementing European Polar research internationally, by specifying overarching priorities, research needs and specific actions. The PEG is comprised of internationally recognised experts in all kinds of Polar Research, including representatives from the EU Polar Cluster projects, Indigenous researchers and researchers from business, NGOs or other stakeholders performing research in the Polar Regions.

6 Evaluation criteria

6.2 Compliance with the content of the present call

- Is the offer rightly focused on contributing to the research prioritisation process of EU-PolarNet 2?
- Does the offer not duplicate activities foreseen in EU-PolarNet 2?

6.3 Quality of the offer

- Is the focus of the offer with respect to the EU-PolarNet 2 project well defined?
- Are the objectives of the offer well thought out and clearly stated?
- Is the stake- and right holder community well targeted and involved (composition, type of involvement...)?
- Is the implementation of the service coherent with respect to its objectives: management, approaches and tools
- Is the proposed work expected to provide added value to the EU-PolarNet 2 project?
- Is the expected service impact well assessed, measured, feasible and realistic?
- Are dissemination activities addressing the general public/stakeholders/research community planned?

6.4 Tasks, budget, timing

- Adequacy of tasks and relevance of their distribution in the Action network with respect to the objectives of the offer.
- Adequacy of the timing.
- Fair and adequate distribution of resources. Since EU-PolarNet 2 is offering service contracts the criteria of best value for money and provisions of conflict of interest³ apply.

7 Reporting

Within one month after completion of the service contract, the service provider must submit a report to EU-PolarNet 2 of the work performed, a short description of the recommended research activities and a publishable summary for dissemination. It must explicitly refer to and comment on the fulfilment of the points of the work plan outlined in the offer.

A reporting template will be provided to the successful service providers.

EU-PolarNet 2 will include the outcome of the service contract in its recommendations for future polar research topics to the EC and for its discussions with national and international funding agencies and thus, gives the successful service providers the opportunity to introduce their research ideas to decision makers.

8 Annexes

ANNEXE 8.1: Eligibility criteria, funding conditions and submission guidelines - first call for services.

ANNEXE 8.2 Application form- first call for services.

Both documents are available on the website: <https://eu-polarnet.eu/call/>

Call for Services

Call 2021

Information guidelines
for service providers

Closing date: 30 September 2021 - 14h00 CET

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1. EU-POLARNET 2

EU-PolarNet 2 is an EU project funded in Horizon 2020. It is composed of 25 partners representing all European Member States and Associated Countries with well-established Polar Programmes. The project has been implemented to improve the coordination of polar research, to identify and prioritise polar research themes of high societal relevance and to support and advise European decision makers on topics related to the Polar regions.

2. CALLS FOR SERVICES

One of the objectives of EU-PolarNet 2 is to prioritise and specify the key societally relevant Polar research themes, which have been defined in the [European Polar Research Programme \(EPRP\)](#), the EU-PolarNet White Papers and in European Polar strategies.

With launching calls for services, EU-PolarNet 2 seeks support from the European Polar Community to further develop research ideas into achievable research projects that could be funded on a national, European or international level. The research themes shall be based on the research needs defined in the EPRP and shall contribute to specific key questions - see section 3.

EU-PolarNet 2 offers up to **15.000 €** financial support to **European (early career) researchers and/or stake- and rightholders** as seed money to cultivate ideas into research projects of wide European interest and high societal relevance. The service contract can be used to organise international workshops and meetings, e.g. for preparing White Papers or joint research proposals, to invite e.g. stake- and rightholders or early career researchers, to perform pre-studies or for any other method leading to the expected outcome.

EU-PolarNet 2 will launch three calls for services in the next three years.

Who is eligible to submit an offer?

Service providers must meet the following eligibility criteria:

1. **Type:** the call for services is open to European (early career) researchers and/or stake- and rightholders, hereafter named service providers.
2. **Affiliation:** The service providers need to be based in a European Member State or in a country that is associated to the EU framework programme¹.
3. **Partnership:** offers must involve partners from at least two different countries. This requirement supports the spirit of international cooperation.
4. **Dissemination:** Only service providers that are entitled to and willing to disseminate the knowledge they will generate under the contract are eligible. A dissemination plan must be included. Service providers must agree to comply with the [EU's General Data Protection Regulation](#).

We especially encourage the inclusion of Early Career researchers and the formation of transdisciplinary networking between researchers and stake- and rightholders relevant to the topic and/or region.

For more information about the project, the European Polar Research Programme and the various thematic areas, please see <https://eu-polarnet.eu/>.

¹ Proponents from Associated Countries can participate under the same conditions as proponents from the Member States. The following countries have indicated that they will associate to Horizon Europe: Iceland, Norway, Albania, Bosnia and Herzegovina, North Macedonia, Montenegro, Serbia, Turkey, Israel, Moldova, Switzerland, Faroe Islands, Ukraine, Tunisia, Georgia, Armenia; UK.

3. SCOPE OF THE 2021 CALL FOR SERVICES

The first EU-PolarNet 2 call for services asks to formulate achievable research activities or projects related to **one of the key questions/sub-topics** of **two of the Research Needs of the EPRP**.

3.1. PROSPERING COMMUNITIES IN THE ARCTIC

This includes the following key questions:

- An infrastructure plan in support of sustainable community development.
- National and sub-national governance challenges in the Arctic Regions.
- Economic innovations for sustainable development of Arctic communities.
- Education as a tool to expand the capacity of Arctic residents to respond to changes.
- Learning from the past for a socio-economically balanced and gender-equal development of the Polar Regions.
- The demography of the future Arctic population.
- Cultural vitality for prosperity in the Arctic.

3.2. INCLUSIVE CREATION, ACCESS AND USAGE OF KNOWLEDGE

This includes the following key questions:

- Developing new technologies and improved capacities in observation, modelling, and research in the Polar regions.
- Co-production of knowledge as a benefit to societal stakeholders.
- FAIR data management principles for polar data collections.
- Ensuring knowledge access and capacity building in Polar Regions.
- Exploiting knowledge to inform decision making for the Polar Regions.

Both research needs are described in detail in the [EPRP](#).

Implementation of the service contract

The implementation of the service contract will require **tools and/or approaches** to be effective and achieve its objectives. For example, site visits and conferences, workshops, desk studies, setting up networks, web interfaces or fora, platforms, measures to promote stakeholders' involvement, are all tools and approaches through which the project's objectives can be achieved.

Tasks, timing and budget

The service provider(s) shall provide a description of tasks - and their distribution amongst the project partners if applicable - and a timing of activities.

The duration of a service contract is **12 months** maximum as of the signature of the contract, for a maximum budget of **15.000€**. This budget is allocated to the service provider(s) and shall cover all expenses considered necessary for successfully implementing the proposed activities such as personnel, operational and travel costs.

The total budget of this call is 40.000€.

4. GUIDELINES FOR COMPLETING THE OFFER

Please read these instructions carefully before completing the submission file.

4.1. SECTION I OF THE SUBMISSION FILE: ADMINISTRATIVE INFORMATION

Title and acronym of the offer and contact details of the service provider(s).

Provide a brief CV of the service provider(s) (5 pages maximum each), also indicating their respective roles in the project and their experiences related to the topic. Please, follow the regulations in terms of affiliations for the teams as stated in the eligibility criteria.

4.2. SECTION II OF THE SUBMISSION FILE: DESCRIPTION OF THE SERVICE

4.2.1. Objectives, impact and implementation plan

Describe the Service by addressing the following points:

a. Objectives of the proposed project:

Provide a clear description of the objectives to be achieved with the proposed project. What is the expected added value to the present state of knowledge?

b. Relation to EU-PolarNet 2

How do the foreseen activities link with the EPRP objectives and what is the added value of the proposed activities or work in this respect?

c. Impact

Provide a clear description on how the proposed topic will contribute to societal needs, even in the long run, by i.e. addressing critical issues related to climate change, environment, or any other benefit for society.

d. Transdisciplinary networking

Include information on how researchers and relevant stake- and/or rightholders will cooperate in the proposed work.

e. Implementation:

Provide a short description of the tools and approaches that you will use. How will they be implemented to make the project effective? Provide an implementation plan with, tasks, timing, and their distribution between partners.

f. Communication and dissemination

Explain the communication and dissemination activities planned within the project.

4.2.2. Budget and starting date²

The budget for the service is limited to a **maximum** budget of **15.000€**.

Provide a breakdown of the budget by category of expenses and provide a justification on each category:

- Personnel costs
- Operational costs (e.g. costs for a workshop, catering, printing etc.)
- Travel costs and invitations to workshops

Indicate your preference for the starting date of your service: between 1 December 2021 and 30 June 2022.

5. PROCEDURES

This paragraph describes the procedures for submitting a project, the selection procedure and the principal obligations applying to the selected applications.

5.1. HOW TO ANSWER TO THIS CALL?

The service provider(s) is/are asked to **only** use the submission file that is downloadable from the EU-PolarNet 2 website (<https://eu-polarnet.eu/call/>). Only applications that fulfil all the eligibility criteria will be considered (see 5.2.2.a).

The application must be sent in English and only electronically (**in pdf format, unprotected, 5 MB max.**) to the following address:

info@eu-polarnet.eu

To facilitate the treatment of the application it is asked to include in the "subject" of the email "[Acronym Project]" and to rename the file in the format: **EUPolarNet2Service_[Acronym Project].pdf**.

The application must be submitted to no later than:

30th September 2021 - 14h00 CET

**Offers submitted after the above-mentioned closing date and time will be disregarded.
A receipt will be sent by email within the three working days after reception of the application.**

The submission file can be downloaded from the EU-PolarNet 2 website at the following address:

[https://eu-polarnet.eu /call/](https://eu-polarnet.eu/call/)

² The costs of service providers from EU-PolarNet 2 partner institutions (beneficiaries) have to be declared via the respective project partner. Please contact the respective beneficiary or info@eu-polarnet.eu.

5.2. EVALUATION AND SELECTION

5.2.1. Selection procedure

The evaluation procedure and selection of research offers will be organised by the EU-PolarNet 2 consortium and performed by its Polar Expert Group (PEG). The PEG is the EU-PolarNet 2 Expert Forum for implementing European Polar research internationally, by specifying overarching priorities, research needs and specific actions. The PEG is comprised of internationally recognised experts in all kinds of Polar Research, including representatives from the EU Polar Cluster projects, Indigenous researchers and researchers from business, NGOs or other stakeholders performing research in the Polar Regions. More information about the PEG can be found [here](#).

5.2.2. Evaluation criteria

The general evaluation criteria to be taken into consideration by the experts are the following:

a. Eligibility

For all submitted offers, the following eligibility criteria are examined:

- The submission file is complete.
- The submission file was submitted in electronic format (in pdf).
- The submission file was submitted no later than 30th September 2021 - 14h00 CET.
- **Research theme:** offers must be related **one of the key questions** described in section 3.
- **International cooperation:** offers must involve partners from at least two different countries. This requirement supports the spirit of international cooperation.
- The duration of the funding of the service is maximum **12 months**.
- The applications must comply with the budget requirements.

Only the Actions that meet **ALL** these criteria will be evaluated.

b. Compliance with the content of the present call

- Is the offer rightly focused on contributing to the research prioritisation process of EU-PolarNet 2?
- Does the offer not duplicate activities foreseen in EU-PolarNet 2?

c. Quality of the offer

- Is the focus of the offer with respect to the EU-PolarNet 2 project well defined?
- Are the objectives of the offer well thought out and clearly stated?
- Is the stake- and right holder community well targeted and involved (composition, type of involvement...)?
- Is the implementation of the service coherent with respect to its objectives: management, approaches and tools
- Is the proposed work expected to provide added value to the EU-PolarNet 2 project?
- Is the expected service impact well assessed, measured, feasible and realistic?
- Are dissemination activities addressing the general public/stakeholders/research community planned?

d. Tasks, budget, timing

- Adequacy of tasks and relevance of their distribution in the Action network with respect to the objectives of the offer.

- Adequacy of the timing.
- Fair and adequate distribution of resources. Since EU-PolarNet 2 is offering service contracts the criteria of best value for money and provisions of conflict of interest³ apply.

6. CONTACTS

Further information can be obtained by contacting:

info@eu-polarnet.eu

7. PRINCIPAL OBLIGATIONS

7.1. REPORTING

Within one month after completion of the service contract, the service provider **must submit a report to EU-PolarNet 2** of the work performed, a short description of the recommended research activities and a publishable summary for dissemination. It must explicitly refer to and comment on the fulfilment of the points of the work plan outlined in the offer.

This report must be submitted in pdf to info@eu-polarnet.eu. **A reporting template will be provided to the successful service providers.**

EU-PolarNet 2 will include the outcome of the service contract in its recommendations for future polar research topics to the EC and for its discussions with national and international funding agencies and thus, gives the successful service providers the opportunity to introduce their research ideas to decision makers.

7.2. FREEDOM OF INFORMATION & DATA PROTECTION

Personal information supplied to EU-PolarNet 2 will be stored electronically (e.g. database) for use only in connection with the handling of offers. All personal data supplied to EU-PolarNet 2 shall be processed in accordance with the Belgium Data Protection Act of 1992, as modified by the law of December 11, 1998 implementing Directive 95/46/EC entering into force in 2001, on the protection of individuals with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data. You have the right to access and update the personal information about you and to ask for such information to be deleted.

All data processing activities, commencing after 25th of May 2018, will comply with the General Data Protection Regulation (replacing the EC Directive 95/46).

All service providers who wish to query the outcome of their application and seek for clarification may contact EU-PolarNet 2 at info@eu-polarnet.eu.

7.3. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

All results/publications/presentations/publicity arising from an EU-PolarNet 2 service contract must acknowledge the funding source, referring to that **this project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the service contract agreement No 101003766 (EU-PolarNet 2)**. Logos for presentations can be found on the [project website](#).

³ EU-PolarNet 2 must take all measures to prevent any situation where the impartial and objective implementation of the service contract is compromised for reasons involving economic interest, political or national affinity, family or emotional ties or any other shared interest.

Call for Services

Offer submission file

Closing date: 30 September 2021 - 14h00 CET

The application should be as concise as possible to ease the proposal evaluation. A font size of Calibri 11 pt should be used with 14 pt spacing.

The application must be sent **electronically (pdf only)** with subject "EUPolarNet2Service_[Acronym Project]" and renamed in the format "[Acronym Service].pdf" to: **info@eu-polarnet.eu**

Service acronym:

SECTION I: ADMINISTRATIVE INFORMATION

I.1 TITLE AND ACRONYM OF THE OFFER

.....

I.2 INFORMATION ON THE SERVICE PROVIDER(S)

Rows to be added if necessary.

	First and last name	Affiliation: Institution, Department/unit, Country	E-mail
Coordinator (partner 1)			
Partner 2			
...			

Please provide a **brief CV** of the service provider(s) (**5 pages maximum each**), also indicating their **respective roles in the project** and their **experience related to the topic**. The CVs should be added as an appendix at the end of the offer.

SECTION II: DESCRIPTION OF THE SERVICE

II.1. OBJECTIVES, IMPACT AND IMPLEMENTATION PLAN

**Please consult the information file for detailed instructions.
DO NOT EXCEED 5 PAGES FOR THIS SECTION**

a) Objectives, impact and implementation plan

.....

b) Relation to EU-PolarNet 2

.....

c) Impact

.....

d) Stake- and rightholder involvement

Service acronym: _____

.....

e) Implementation:

.....

f) Communication and dissemination

.....

II.2. BUDGET AND STARTING DATE

g) Overall budget

	Budget requested in EURO	Justification
Staff		
Consumables		
Travel		
Other goods and services		
TOTAL		

h) Starting date

Please indicate if you have a preferred starting date. The starting date should lie in between 1 December 2021 – 30 June 2022.

Preferred Starting Date / No Preference: